

Herbarium best practices: The importance of addressing curatorial work (preservation and stabilisation of the specimens) especially prior to digitisation endeavours

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.14008175](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14008175)

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ABSTRACT

Curatorial work has been cited as part of digitisation workflows, though with discussions often centred on the benefit of improving the efficiency of the digitisation process. The curatorial work referred here is about ensuring the preservation and, stabilisation of the specimens, rather than the benefit in making the specimens look aesthetically better when imaged. The underlying reasons why this work should be conducted (as an obligation) have been given little attention but should be discussed and exposed what would be the benefits in addressing the curatorial needs particularly prior to a digitisation project, and what could be the possible risks if these are not implemented. Here we address the importance of making efforts to carry out the essential care and preservation of the botanical specimens, and we suggest what could be the minimum standards that should be followed and adhered to. We highlight not only the possible bottlenecks in the efficiency of the digitisation process (which secures access to the collections digitally), but also the necessity of maintaining the condition and accessibility of the physical collection (raw resource) which the digital process cannot replace or may not be found in other specimens.

Keywords: best practices, collections, curation, herbarium, preservation, pre-digitisation, specimens

INTRODUCTION

Digitisation projects, particularly those involving herbarium collections, have become part of almost every institution's day-to-day activity. These have been seen across herbaria worldwide at different scales and priorities for more than four decades. In addition to financial constraints, limited time and personnel have been the primary factors slowing digitisation processes. In order to improve this, institutions have been exploring all possible technologies and approaches to reduce costs and upgrade efficiency, as the digitisation of a collection is not a simple task and has several layers of complexity.

Digitisation standards have been promoted and publicised, set and agreed, followed and consistently applied. The proof of this is the number of publications and projects mentioning them (e.g. Nelson et al. 2015; Guiraud et al. 2019; Thompson & Birch 2023; De Smedt et al., 2024) and the word 'digitisation' dominating the titles for most if not all of these publications. Many of these papers focused solely on the digitisation process, with little attention on the associated curatorial work, which, most of the time, was only included as a component of the workflow, or cited as part of the process with a few extra steps, in order to avoid bottlenecks on the digitisation work.

Detailed information, definitions, guidelines and/or illustrations of the digitisation process are usually included, while less coverage has been given to the description of the curatorial phase (or specimen workflows), despite the greater amount of time, the various types of work needed, and effort involved (when and if carried out in this stage of the process).

There are, however, a few publications that attempted to explain some of the steps of the mentioned curatorial work (Nelson et al. 2012, 2015; De Smedt et al. 2024), though, none have explicitly given the reasons why this work should be carried out, apart from helping improving digitisation efficiency or the image aesthetics.

The aims of this paper are, to promote and emphasise the importance of the pre-digitisation curatorial work ('specimen workflow', 'curative work', as being referred to in some papers); to discuss the benefits of having curatorial work carried out in advance; to highlight the possible risks of not having adequate resources (i.e. time and personnel) to complete thorough curatorial work, or the preservation and stabilisation of the specimens; and to set what could be designated as the minimum standards for curatorial best practices, especially prior to any digitisation project. Additionally, this paper will provide the basics on what preservation and collections care of the herbarium specimens means and entails.

BACKGROUND

Looking at the history of digitisation projects carried out at the Natural History Museum, London (NHM, here and thereafter), digitisation of the type collections (between 1999 to 2003) was, as in many other institutions, the starting point of efforts in digitising a collection set. Over the years, other projects came along, with different foci, purposes and timelines. Based on these past projects, valuable conclusions have been drawn and best practices have been gathered, particularly for those that refer to curatorial work, which has been noticed throughout the collections that have been digitised.

The projects related to the digitisation of type specimens (i.e. API: African Plants Initiative, GPI: Global Plants Initiative) at NHM did not have any component of curatorial work. On the other hand, the project that involved the botanical order Brassicales (Baker et al., 2019) took a more thorough approach with substantial curatorial work employed and addressed prior to its digitisation. Unlike other, funded projects, this was delivered with the support of the NHM's volunteers programme (Yesilyurt et al., 2016) and by NHM digitisation team (by imaging the prepared specimens).

The curatorial workflow (Fig. 1) of the Brassicales project was based on an activity (called herbarium check-up) that was carried out as part of the weekly tasks for curators. This workflow has been changing to improve efficiency in both curatorial and digitisation processes. Since then, it has been adopted and adapted across various herbarium digitisation projects in-house, and always accommodated according to the available resources (time and personnel).

Figure 1: Workflow followed for the Brassicales project. Tasks performed by curators (green) volunteers (orange) and data managers/digitisation team (yellow). Steps marked in grey are part of the databasing and digitisation stages, not discussed in this paper.

The ‘herbarium check-up’ or ‘specimen workflow’ comprised the following tasks: a) checking that specimens are in the right filling geographical region (used in the herbarium organisation); b) checking that specimens are in the correct (taxonomic) species folder, here referred to by ‘filed as’ name; c) checking and addressing specimens with new determination (det, here and thereafter), and re-curation (filed under the correct ‘filed as’ name as on the det label); d) checking the housing condition of the folders, thinning and/or replacing tattered or damaged (from genus and species) folders; e) checking if the specimens required preservation and stabilization tasks, such as: i) cleaning the herbarium sheets of dust and soot; ii) replacing old, damaged straps and/or adding extra straps for reinforcement and stabilisation; iii) adding capsules to capture any loose, detached materials on the sheets; f) checking if specimens would need replacement of any non-archival material such as paper clips and pins, and/or removal of plastic covers; and g) annotating the herbarium sheets (following guidelines) with the number of the: geographical region, family and genus numbers (which follows our collections organisation).

For major repairing and conservation work, the specimen would be removed to be dealt with by the plant mounters team. For example: a) when the whole specimen has been detached or has signs of various damages; b) the herbarium sheet has shown severe deterioration signs, which in some cases, it would need to be totally re-mounted; c) specimens mounted on much smaller sheet, which could also contain information on the back of the sheet, these would be inserted on big capsule which would be mounted on the standard herbarium sheet. In addition to the above tasks, capturing 'filed as' names, was also part of the curatorial work although this would usually precede the above tasks. Generally, this would be carried out by noting the names from the species folders, without removing them from the shelves/cabinets, thus avoiding unnecessary handling. Those specimens with new determinations, would be picked up during the above-mentioned tasks (steps a-c).

As mentioned earlier, the Brassicales project had support from a team of volunteers (at least 10 of them working together plus three that already knew the process, to provide extra support for the curators), who had received specialised intensive training. The team of volunteers was replaced (and trained) every three months, following Museum's programme on that time. Having volunteers to help, is not always an option in many institutions; in such cases, the work would be performed by the curator/s, and probably accommodated within other day-to-day tasks.

Recently, due to short of resources and time pressures in preparing the collections for the forthcoming digitisation projects, the workflow has been modified and streamlined (Fig. 2). This change also anticipates possible cutbacks in resources that an institution may have to devote to the pre digitisation curatorial work. Although in a much shorter process, it will give the opportunity to carry out the essential work (preservation, stabilisation) needed. While some institutions might manage to have extra resources and/or employ new professional digitisers to carry out the tasks (database and imaging), in others, the curators would need to take up the digitiser's role (thus reducing the time for the curatorial role). It is important though, to recognise the differences and the needs of these two individual roles in the digitisation process/projects due to their specialism and expertise, as stated by Flemons & Berents (2012). These roles need to co-exist and work in synergy, to achieve the same goals, but where a curator needs to cover the digitisation aspects, then this should be split 50:50.

Figure 2: Workflow with only essential curatorial work. Tasks performed by curators (green) and volunteers (orange). Dotted lines indicate that this step would be carried out once the list of ‘filed as names’ has been captured. In the absence of volunteers, the curator would perform all the work, from capturing the names, addressing curatorial and preservation needs of the specimens.

Curatorial work: setting the standards

Despite some references having had embedded curatorial tasks on the workflows for digitising a collection (e.g. (Nelson et al., 2012, 2015; De Smedt et al., 2024), the emphasis has usually been on the digitisation steps (here referring to databasing and imaging), to ensure protocols and standards are followed.

There are a few publications that refer to the type of curatorial work needed prior to a digitisation project taking place (e.g. De Smedt et al., 2024; Nelson et al., 2015; Thompson & Birch, 2023), however none has emphasised the importance of setting the standards and reinforcing that, best practices (with curatorial work prior to the digitisation) should be followed and adopted without compromise. Moreover, the impacts and possible risks the herbarium specimens could endure, if this step is neglected, have not yet been discussed or stated.

In this paper, we would like to emphasise the need to adhere to best practices and suggest the minimum standards that should be set, not only as part of pre digitisation work, but also as

part of the routine herbarium procedures to make the collections enduring and useful. The need to advise may seem redundant but there have been projects that did not incorporate time and resources in the plan for the curatorial work. This essential and critical work should not be compromised, as it can also help towards avoiding bottlenecks in the digitisation process (and avoid some of the post-digitisation work that might arise as a consequence of neglecting these practices).

Despite many of the digitisation projects having happened more than a decade ago, what has been known about the impacts of not having a thorough curatorial work carried out, is anecdotal (heard elsewhere or mentioned in-house). It is also important to mention that these risks are not solely linked to the digitisation endeavours; they could also be the result of poor handling and/or curatorial neglect not addressing conservation needs. For example, missing or having detached morphological structures (such as flowers and/or fruits) that have not been rescued and addressed promptly. These could affect the ability, for instance, to have a correct determination of the specimen, or compromising the designation as original material (if compared with what has been described on the protologue during the process of designation of types, where specimen would bear flowers and/or fruits). These are just two examples demonstrating how important the curatorial work is (particularly those aspects referring to preservation and stabilisation of the specimen/s) as they could have been prevented, preserved, rescued. Potential uses of the herbarium specimens, addressing a wide range of scientific questions are increasing (e.g. Carine et al., 2018; Funk, 2018; Rønsted et al., 2020; Swain & Chakraborty, 2024), indicating that we should put all efforts to maintain and preserve every little fragment of the herbarium specimens, especially those which might have uses that are not currently recognised. The curatorial work means not only taking care of rescuing loose parts, but also stabilising and maintaining the specimen, following best practices and the defined standards advised here.

A recent paper (De Smedt et al., 2024) has listed ten lessons learned from a digitisation project. One of these is to “*repair and restore the specimens that may not be in optimal condition, by checking across the collections, and address those specimens with cellophane, plastic bags, and transferring loose material to envelopes*”. The concept of a “collection in optimal condition” can be interpreted in different ways. Cellophane and plastic bags (a curatorial approach that has been seen in certain herbaria, or for certain specimens, including at the NHM, where it has been used to prevent opening up and dispersal of the seeds/flowers), certainly impacts on image quality. Freeing the specimens from this

‘protective’ material can cause some damage upon removal, due to the electrostatic reaction, and due care must be taken to remove it and rescue loose parts (including those that will be attached to the cellophane/plastic bag). This material is not appropriate to be used and different approaches should be looked if protection is required.

De Smedt et al. (2024) also stated that the curatorial work pre digitisation was intense in the first phase (i.e. first mass digitisation that has taken place in the institution), while in the second phase, the ‘restoration efforts were drastically reduced (limited only to ‘new arrivals’). The interpretation of reduction in the curatorial work pre digitisation being (reduced and) limited to the new arrivals, has been attributed to the fact that the specimens most probably needed to be mounted and stabilised (and/or they might have been new acquisitions). Such circumstances have also been reported by Giraud et al. (2019), when they stated that curatorial work was needed (i.e. mounting the specimens) as the condition of the specimens affected the rate of imaging.

Every specimen should be independently inspected, and at least the first three (of the four) “*essential procedures*” listed below should be addressed and be the foundation of any work involving herbarium collections.

Essential procedures:

I- Rescuing loose parts of the specimen: This is the most essential work to be carried out as part of herbarium procedures and collections care. Loose parts, pieces, and other elements linked to the specimen (no matter the size, and state) should be salvaged as these can be the sole source of raw data/information of the specimen from a particular place and time, and which may not be present in other specimens. Once lost, these cannot be replaced or recovered, and is therefore different from all other curatorial work, in which neglected objects or curatorial mistakes (e.g. wrong transcription, poor quality image, geographically misfiled), can, in principle, be corrected, re-done and/or replaced (Figs. 3A, 3B).

II- Capsules: Capsules should be added to specimens wherever possible, if one does not exist already (this is obligatory when mounting new specimens). They are important in cases/eventualities where pieces of material are broken, or detached, they can be rescued immediately and properly safeguarded. Everything should be rescued and added to the capsule (please note that only loose materials that definitely belong to the specimen, should be captured/salvaged, and not any material found elsewhere, so to avoid contamination).

Although the ideal would be to add a capsule to every specimen that does not have one (it is a

time-consuming task), this decision is made on case-by-case basis. However, we present here some criteria that could help towards this decision, in addition to those specimens that need immediate rescue of the loose parts: i) specimens that are pre-1900s. This may not seem to be a practical suggestion, especially for those institutions (as NHM), that hold a rich collection from these times. In these cases, further prioritization could be made, and address only those specimens with multiple collections/material or those that might look prone to be damaged/detached (Figs. 3A, 3B, 4A); ii) specimens representative of special attributes, such as, historical importance, special collectors/areas, extinct in the wild; iii) specimens with multiple collections/material post-1900s (Fig. 4B). In these cases, space might be a problem to attach various capsules (as in Fig 4A), however, one capsule must be added which could house other smaller capsules (properly labelled), if needed, from the different material of the sheet.

III- Specimen stabilisation: Specimens should be inspected and where needed, preservation and stabilisation of the material should be addressed promptly, by strapping/re-strapping (or securing by key point adhesion, and only where necessary). This would help maintain and preserve the specimen from further deterioration. This work usually can be carried out on the spot, however, if specimens need major work these should be removed and addressed accordingly (e.g. some specimens may need to be totally re-mounted due to herbarium sheet deterioration).

IV- Housing condition: If time and resources allow, this task should be carried out while performing the herbarium checking-up, otherwise this work can be addressed after the digitisation if there are no areas with major concerns about possible damages to the specimens. Under the new workflow (Fig. 2), thinning the folders would have high priority when these are overcrowded and posing risks to the specimens, due to the edges creating friction with the material (Fig.5B). Similar work should be carried out within the shelves, so the folders/specimens can be moved in and out comfortably, without posing risks of breakages/damages to the specimens (Fig. 5A).

Any loose labels should be attached to the specimen; non-archival materials such as pins and paper clips should be removed or replaced.

The task involving capturing 'Filed as names', can be carried out prior the curatorial work or during the herbarium check-up/housing condition work (if this would be required prior to databasing). Taxonomic needs could be spotted during the above procedures (i.e. sheet with

new determinations). However, species folders without ‘filed as’ names written or unclear, should be addressed promptly as this step can improve and reduce any bottleneck during the process of databasing, since some taxonomic knowledge might be required and can take some time to resolve it.

Absence of Collections Care and Management Procedures can impact the efficiency of the digitisation process. However, the biggest impact would be on the loss of data (raw material and information) and on the devaluation of the specimen, which, one may not be able to retrieve, recover or replace afterwards or ever again.

Figure 3: Examples of specimens pre 1900s. 3A: Example of multiple specimens. During the herbarium check up, a fruit has detached (red circles) from the specimen and if not spotted immediately, it could have been easily mistaken and assigned to the wrong specimen (the one with various fruits, since it has a missing fruit already; marked in yellow). 3B: Example of specimen with high priority. This specimen has one single tiny flower (in detail) therefore, a capsule should be added in case this flower detaches from the specimen, so it can be rescued promptly.

Figure 4: Examples of multiple specimens where capsule/s should be added. 4A: example of pre 1900s specimen, with space to add a capsule for each material. 4B: example of multiple specimens with restricted space: at least one capsule should be added. Mini capsules can be added inside the main capsule, if needed, properly labelled to identify from which material the content belongs.

Figure 5: Examples of overfilled shelves and crowded/tatty folders. 5A: Overfilled shelves, posing difficulties to move folders in and out, without putting the specimens at risk of breakage/damage. Also, under these conditions will not be possible to incorporate new specimens. 5B: Examples of folders (genus and species) that should be thinned and replaced.

They are not housing and protecting the specimens accordingly, as specimens are exposed and under risk of damages due to the edges of the folders fractioning with/the specimens/material.

Curation for preservation and accessibility

Digitisation certainly creates a digital surrogate of an object and, as a result, the risks associated with handling are reduced significantly, since the digital specimen can replace the physical in many enquiries. This conforms with what has been stated by Corona (2023), that digitisation allows us to ‘preserve the collections’, and by Marín-Rodulfo et al. (2024), that the use of these digital resources helps to preserve the physical specimen for purposes that the ‘digital specimen’ cannot serve (e.g., molecular studies).

However, one can dispute/contest this, as in fact, an effective and long-lasting preservation would only be, if the specimen is conserved, stable and well cared for, and if a proper ‘preservation’ has been carried out prior to the handling to create a digital surrogate. In other words, the *“appropriateness of collections management plays a crucial role in preserving collections”* (Corona 2023), though one needs to accept that this is so, when curatorial work (i.e. collections management and care) is carried out, at all times. This is particularly the case, with the digitisation process as it has various stages, where specimens could be handled at least two times or more. Thompson & Birch (2023) have demonstrated that in some cases, a specimen could be handled or moved up to 10 times during the digitisation process (Thompson & Birch, 2023, Fig. 22, pag. 25).

The consequences of losing even those tiny elements that could be/are, crucial to the integrity and value of the specimen, could impact on the accessibility (and usefulness, including of the image, if it has not been taken prior the ‘damage/loss’) of this resource, which could be relevant to answering scientific questions. Therefore, it is fundamental to carry out (and address) the basic essential curatorial work, at any stage, prior to moving specimen/s around.

Curation post-digitisation: what can be left

Past experiences from working with the collections for digitisation (at NHM) gave the opportunity to understand each stage of the curatorial work (e.g. workflow Fig. 1) and which aspects of this process, could compromise on, and be compromised for, the digitisation workflow. It also gave insights on which steps of the curatorial work could be carried out post digitisation.

Taking the digitisation of the order Brassicales project (carried out between 2017-2018) as an example, this covered ca. 52,000 Brassicales herbarium specimens (Baker et al., 2019), of which ca 75 specimens have been misfiled taxonomically including some newly determined specimens and ca. 35, geographically (according to the herbarium organisation). These figures were based on the material that were being worked on throughout the whole project. It does not mean though, that there will not be misfiled specimens, considering that the project has had various stages, workstations, and a big team of volunteers. On the other hand, at least 60% of the total specimens needed some attention, regarding preservation and conservation work, which included cleaning the sheets from dust and soot, adding straps or key-point adhesion (straps used in the past were not good quality, so they have detached or have been torn, as well as the glue used in the past, has become acidic and brittle, detaching the specimens) and adding capsules.

Similar figures (of specimens needing recuration and/or preservation) have been also recorded for the project with the order Malvales (which contain ca 51,000 specimens, see Yesilyurt et al., 2024). Interestingly, Paul & Nelson (2012) mentioned on their pre-digitisation curation tasks that some institutions (there wasn't any reference as to which institutions) reported that it would expect as many as 50% of specimens for some groups, to require conservation (pre-digitisation). According to them these tasks would remove the specimens from the active digitization workflow and there would be a necessity of design of an efficient re-insertion strategy for returning these specimens. If this work is indeed carried out as pre-digitisation task, the collections would be in place, ready and part of the digitisation workflow, thus avoiding this extra step.

The project focusing the Geraniales Order (ca 5,280 specimens), also received the support from volunteers, where two worked one day per week, between October 2023 until February 2024. This project has highlighted different aspects of what could have gone wrong if the curatorial and collections management work had not been addressed in advance, from

preservation of the specimens to the possible impacts on the efficiency of the digitisation process. The decision-making process to address the taxonomic challenges for this group has taken substantial time, because it required some taxonomic expertise and investigation, as many species folders had only a number (no 'filed as' names). The genera of this order were organised following a phylogenetic systematic treatment, hence the numbering system. However, there were cases where a particular number led to more than three different names; it also had many hybrids, and new determinations. The lack of 'filed as names', on the species folders would certainly create a bottleneck in the digitisation process. On the other hand, most of the specimens from this order, are more contemporaneous material (i.e. after 1930s), and therefore, there were fewer specimens that needed restoration and preservation work. Other areas that required attention were the crowded shelves and overfilled genus/species covers, or specimens that did not have been inside species covers.

Conversely the current projects (carried out with the Myrtales and Gentianales orders) are a completely different story. All previous projects have adopted the workflow in place (Fig. 1), however, when the work started with these orders, a new workflow has been put into practice (Fig. 2), with the aim of speeding up the process without compromising specimen care and preservation. It can easily be added into the flow of the digitisation project, if as may be the case, a mass digitisation programme requires rapid access to the collections, or if resources (time and financial) are short.

The order Myrtales for instance (the work has started recently: June 2024), usually has specimens with bulky areas/structures (e.g. fruits, inflorescences, twigs) and there have been many historical specimens (pre 1900s). So far, it has been noticed that almost every specimen needs some attention, including addressing the specimens with new determinations and the species folders without 'filed as' names. The three main essential tasks will be carried out as described above and any other curatorial work can be and will be addressed post-digitisation, such as:

a) Specimens will not be inspected methodically if they are on the right geographical area; b) nor they will be annotated (with geographical and family/genus number); the exception would be if the specimen does not have any label or annotation; c) genus and species folders will be replaced if these are considerably damaged/tattered and they will be thinned if overfilled and absolutely necessary (e.g. causing friction to the material/specimens, as can be

seen on Fig. 5B); d) cleaning-up will be carried out only if sheets are extremely dirty and particularly on the upper third of the sheet (where the barcode will be usually attached).

During the digitisation of the types projects, any curatorial work has been addressed, however, luckily the type specimens are contained inside their own (4-flap) type folder. This means that any loose material can be rescued without problems/concerns; the exception being when the type folder contains two or more specimen sheets. Conservation and preservation have been addressed for the types, whenever there is an opportunity to work with the type specimens, alongside correcting geographical or taxonomical information and updating the records. The specimens are stabilised by having new or replaced straps, capsules are added where necessary, and loose parts are rescued. In rare cases, the type is re-imaged.

CONCLUSION

The significant amount of work required for the preparation of collections prior to any digitisation process should not be underestimated.

Curatorial work is the element of collections care and management that is certainly the most time-consuming, independently of the level of (amount of) curatorial work required.

Specimen handling tasks (preservation and curation) are typically labour-intensive steps (Thompson & Birch, 2023), even if it is just retrieving the specimen for imaging, if comparing with imaging or databasing tasks (time wise).

Having well-curated collections (i.e. preservation and conservation of the specimens), as part of the preparation for digitisation will make the whole process of digitisation run more smoothly, thus considerably reducing the need for work afterwards.

Institutions may have a number of reasons which would impact any decision on the amount of time and resources dedicated to the care and preservation of collections prior to the digitisation process. Therefore, this paper can hopefully provide insights into the decision process of planning and allocating resources (time and personnel) to carry out this work. As Thompson & Birch (2023) stated, digitisation workflows must be flexible and adaptable (without compromising quality). We support the same idea for the curatorial workflow, by proposing a flexible and more focussed yet adaptable process, without compromising the standards of care and preservation of the specimens.

Thompson & Birch (2023) also stated that, the requirements would be more effectively achieved when workflows are well documented, contextualised, and understood. Based on this principle, we hope that workflows presented here, where the minimum standards (particularly for pre-digitisation) for curatorial work suggested here are well documented and would be followed and implemented, since they have been contextualised, exemplified and recognised for their efficacy and value.

The (pre digitisation) curatorial work could be addressed following one of the two approaches suggested here: the exhaustive process or just carrying out the essential work. Either one will focus on the specimen/material and not just on the 'object' (herbarium sheet). This is because any damage to, or loss of material in the physical domain cannot be rectified or replaced after digitisation. Whereas any errors in the digital domain (e.g. data entry, images) can be 'restored, salvaged, replaced' or corrected.

The minimum standards for pre-digitisation curatorial work discussed here are intended to address the risks of unrectifiable physical damage to the specimen. The loss (and damage) could not only put the collections at risk, but also diminish the scientific value and sustainability of the specimen (as potential future proof resource). As Silva et al. (2024) stated, prevention should be mandatory, explaining further that, maintaining the specimen/object, is most important than restoring, and it would avoid further degradation that could affect their stability and longevity.

The examples provided here (via projects) have demonstrated that knowing the collections will help to understand where and what would be required to put the efforts to address them (e.g. conservation state or housing conditions and access, which would cover for instance, 'filed as names').

The idea that with the collections digitised, images would help analysing workflows that detect the type of mounting strategy and preservation state of specimens (Groom et al., 2023), thus helping curators triage remounting or other forms of curatorial care can be of assistance. However, we believe that, although images could provide such information, it might be too late to rescue what might have been lost (or contaminated with pieces from other specimens inside the species folders) during the process. This certainly could be the case, where the workflow has specimens handled more than three times. Besides, if there are concerns about the aesthetic and authenticity of the image with the physical specimen, then repairs, adding capsule and/or cleaning, should be addressed prior to the specimen being imaged, otherwise,

if addressed after digitisation, the specimen may need to be re-imaged. Handling without support, fragile or not well stabilised specimens can pose issues, including with images/imaging as commented by Guiraud et al. (2019), “*if your collection is well mounted/restored, the imaging process will be much faster (no loose material that can fall off or can cause bad cropping) and the images will look nicer*”.

It is important to note that, when we refer here to a well curated collections, we are focusing on the care and preservation of the collections/specimens. Other aspect of a well curated collection would be at the taxonomic level. All the work carried out under the projects mentioned here, have addressed those specimens with new determinations, or species covers that didn't have a name (that a specimen would be filed under). Updating the collections (taxonomically) with the current and accepted names, will be a (massive) work which will be carried out, post digitization and which will include the curation of the digital side of the collections, i.e. updating the records.

As a final point, we also believe that the opportunity that a digitisation project may offer, is beyond providing access to the collections digitally. Carrying out the curatorial work prior to digitisation, will be a unique circumstance, as the collections would be audited in terms of preservation and stabilisation of the specimens. It will secure (and re-enforce in certain cases) the access to the physical raw resources, for future generations that may need to meet their research needs under future (unforeseen yet) scenarios. Marin-Rudolfo et al. (2024) commented that specimen loss and deterioration is difficult to overcome; but the truth is that it would be difficult, if not impossible, to replace.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to acknowledge all the volunteers that have worked with us and those that currently are volunteering, helping to deliver some of the projects at the Algae, Fungi and Plants Division. We are also grateful to Dr Mark Carine, for the support on the various projects we have implemented, trying and testing the workflows. Our gratitude is also towards those that provided support with various other aspects of the projects mentioned here (e.g. plant mounters and digitisation team).

Author Contributions: Jovita C. Yesilyurt and Raneer Prakash are Senior Curators at NHM. Jovita C. Yesilyurt: conceived and lead on the conceptualization, writing original draft, reviewed and conducted the final editing; all other co-authors: reviewed early versions, suggested corrections, contributed with some information and/or facts based on the work/volunteered work carried out at the NHM (at the Algae, Fungi and Plants Department) during various projects.

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Conflict of Interest Statement: The corresponding author of the manuscript entitled “*Herbarium best practices: The importance of addressing curatorial work (preservation and stabilisation of the specimens) especially prior to digitisation endeavours*”, on behalf of all contributing authors, hereby declare there are no potential competing interests that might influence any of the work we do at the herbarium at NHM. Should further information or clarification be required, please do not hesitate to contact the corresponding author.